

Obfuscating Convolutional Neural Network Image Classification Using ASCII Character Representation

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Abstract—This study investigates the effectiveness of ASCII transformation as an obfuscation method for image classification tasks. We employed five widely-used convolutional neural network models — VGG19, ResNet50, InceptionV3, MobileNet, and EfficientNetB0 — to classify images of cats and dogs from a dataset both before and after conversion to ASCII representation. The results reveal that ASCII transformation significantly impairs the models’ ability to correctly classify images. Despite using state-of-the-art classifiers with pre-trained weights on ImageNet, none of the models successfully identified any of the cat or dog images in the obfuscated dataset. The analysis further demonstrates that the models are not just misclassifying but are fundamentally misled by the grid structure of ASCII characters. This research underscores the potential of using ASCII transformation as an easily available obfuscation method when evaluated against the current out-of-the-box classifier models.

Index Terms—image classification, convolutional neural networks, image obfuscation, ASCII art

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, image classification based on deep neural networks (DNNs) has achieved remarkable success, significantly improving the ability of machines to recognize and categorize visual content. Landmark achievements include AlexNet’s victory in the 2012 ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC), which demonstrated the effectiveness of deep learning in handling large-scale image datasets [1] [2]. Subsequent models such as VGGNet, ResNet, and Inception have further pushed the boundaries, achieving near-human accuracy in various image recognition tasks [3].

Due to these recent advances, there can be scenarios in which it becomes desirable or necessary to obfuscate images against automatic image classification algorithms. Privacy concerns are paramount, especially in sensitive applications such as medical imaging, social media, and surveillance. In addition, protection of intellectual property, security measures, and preventing unauthorized access to proprietary visual content are other possible reasons to obfuscate images.

ASCII art, a technique of creating images using characters from the ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) character set, has been used historically because of its simplicity and low bandwidth requirements. It originated

in the early days of computer graphics when limitations in display technology necessitated creative approaches to visual representation [4]. Due to the technique’s long history and significance, tools for creating ASCII art from images are readily available and easily accessible, facilitating its easy use. Notable tools include:

- `jp2a`: A Linux-based command-line tool that converts JPEG images to ASCII art.
- `ascii-magic`: A Python library for generating ASCII art from images.
- `Picascii`: Another popular tool that provides similar functionality, often used for artistic purposes and data visualization.

In this paper, I investigate how transforming images into ASCII character representations affects their recognition by deep neural network classifiers. I will explore some parameters involved in this transformation. The aim of this short study is to evaluate the feasibility of using ASCII art as an obfuscation technique, and this study will help us understand how modern DNNs recognize obfuscated images. The question I wish to address is whether ASCII art can be a viable method for obscuring visual content.

To the authors’ knowledge, no directly comparable research has been conducted. Existing studies primarily explore image obfuscation by leveraging the feature spaces of deep neural networks (DNNs). A prominent example of such an approach is `DeepObfuscator` [5] [6], which focuses on obfuscating personal attributes such as identity, age, or gender.

Beyond `DeepObfuscator`, several other techniques have been proposed, with visual comparisons provided, for instance, in Figure 2 of Jeong et al. [7]. In this paper, the focus is on image classification. Yang et al. [8] evaluated the impact of privacy obfuscation on classification tasks and observed only a minor effect on performance.

There also exists two studies which examine the classification of ASCII art using DNNs [9] [10]. However, these studies focused solely on manually drawn ASCII art, such as Fig. 1, rather than pixel images converted to ASCII format.

Fig. 1. Manually created ASCII art images in contrast to ASCII images converted from pixel images (Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ASCII_art)

II. METHODS

In this section, I outline the methodology employed in the study, beginning with a description of the image data set used. Then I present the process by which these images are converted into their ASCII representations, highlighting the transformation techniques and relevant preprocessing steps. Finally, I will present the applied image classification methods.

A. Image Dataset

The selection of a dataset and classification methods depend naturally on the application. For example, it maybe important to hide persons' identities or landmarks for geolocation. The purpose of this study is to provide just an initial overview of the feasibility of image obfuscation by using ASCII presentation. Therefore clear animal images were being sought.

Several large image datasets, including ImageNet, Oxford-IIIT Pet Dataset, and Microsoft COCO, were initially evaluated. The recognizability of objects were estimated by visual inspection. Eventually, a general image dataset by P. Sanaga-pati hosted on Kaggle.com that contains high-quality photos classified into eight categories [11] was chosen. By "general" it is meant that the subjects in the images mostly stand out clearly from the background, and the images are not intended for any specific purpose, such as spatial localization or pose estimation. The chosen image dataset has a "CC0: Public Domain" license and version number used is 1.0.

In Fig. 2, an example image from the dataset is provided.

B. Transformation of Pixel Images to ASCII Presentation

Most common algorithms for converting pixel images to ASCII character representations work in a similar way. Since terminal characters are much bigger than pixels it is common to scale down the image thus leading to some information loss. Additionally, the aspect ratio is adjusted, as pixels are usually square while terminal characters often have greater height than width.

The image may be converted to grayscale, or colors can be processed in layers. Although traditional terminals displayed images in two colors such as black and white, modern terminals use ANSI colors as the standard. For images intended for use in HTML documents, the full RGB color palette can be used.

Each pixel's brightness is then mapped to a corresponding ASCII character based on a predefined density table. Darker pixels are mapped to denser characters, and lighter pixels to sparser characters. It is worth noting that a certain font,

Fig. 2. An image of a cat from the image dataset (data file number 130).

terminal settings, and display properties are presumed. The actual result might therefore have distortions depending on how it is viewed.

An ASCII character representation of the image in Fig. 2 is presented in Fig. 3. The original image is 422 x 500 pixels, aspect ratio 0.844, while the ascii representation is 100 x 53 characters, aspect ratio about 1.887. We can also see that the terminal used here has a slightly higher line density than the algorithm expects, so the image is compressed vertically.

It is difficult to recognize cat in Fig. 3. This is mainly due to the lack of color information. Corresponding ANSI and HTML color versions are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Information loss due to the transform is still easy to recognize by comparing Fig. 2 with Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. For humans, the object is easy to recognize from the original image in Fig. 2. Although the cat is also recognizable from Fig. 4, it presents more uncertainty.

Full RGB color image in Fig. 5 is easy to recognize even though the image appears to be darker than the original due to the dominant black background color. The black background color is important for human eyes to recognize character colors. For comparison, the same ASCII character presentation with white background color is shown in Fig. 6. For human eyes, it is difficult to recognize the character colors and the object in the image.

Generally, good source material is needed, with possible preprocessing, to produce well recognizable ASCII character

images. For human eyes, high enough resolution and retaining color information is often sufficient. Even in this image dataset selected for high clarity images, not all images were usable for human recognition after automatic ASCII transformation. Therefore, only a subset of images was chosen to be used, containing ten cat images and ten dog images that represent photos clearly identifiable for humans.

I find using a small dataset is justified in this context, as our objective is simply to assess the feasibility of the method. The analysis of twenty images should give us a preliminary indication of whether this topic is worth further investigation.

C. Classification Procedure

In this study, I use popular out-of-the-box convolutional neural network classifiers. Classifiers need to be trained using an image dataset. One of the largest and highest quality datasets in machine learning and computer vision research is ImageNet. It contains over 14 million images categorized into more than 20,000 distinct classes, with a focus on object recognition. [12]

Each image in the dataset is annotated with labels from the WordNet hierarchy, which allows the classification of a wide variety of objects, including animals, objects, and scenes. ImageNet is widely used for training and evaluating neural network classifiers due to its extensive and diverse set of labeled images.

In this study, I chose the following convolutional neural network models: VGG19 [13], ResNet50 [14], InceptionV3 [15], MobileNet [16], and EfficientNetB0 [17]. These models were selected due to their proven effectiveness and the availability of pretrained weights on the ImageNet dataset.

Additionally, these models represent a diverse range of architectures — from deeper and more complex networks like ResNet50 and InceptionV3 to lightweight and efficient designs such as MobileNet and EfficientNetB0 — allowing for an assessment of classification performance across various network types. Systematic image obfuscation, such as the ASCII transformation, could potentially reveal differences between different CNN architectures.

D. Dataset Preprocessing

Upon preliminary examination, it became evident that the images from the selected dataset presented significant challenges following the ASCII transformation. This was despite the initial selection of a clear image dataset. Most images became unrecognizable even to the human eye when transformed into 100-column-wide ASCII representations. Consequently, a smaller subset of images was initially chosen for analysis. This subset consists of images that are clearly identifiable for humans.

Also, it became apparent that the transformation to ASCII representation poses even greater challenges for Neural Network Classifiers. As a result, the scope of the task was narrowed to the basic detection of typical cat and dog images. The following 10 images were selected from each category (numbering corresponds to file names in the dataset):

Cats: 104, 106, 107, 111, 115, 130, 133, 145, 154, 160

Dogs: 12, 103, 104, 105, 108, 113, 117, 123, 125, 132

ImageNet does not have cat and dog as classification categories *per se* but they are presented by a wide variety of breeds and related species. For the category of cat, ImageNet has five classes of domestic cats and seven classes of wild cats. All these are considered valid identification for the class cat. For dogs, there are 120 different breeds including close relative species of dingo. All of these were grouped together to form an acceptable class of dogs in this study.

E. Methodology

The reference dataset, preprocessed from the original dataset, contains two sets of images: cats and dogs. The experimental obfuscated datasets were generated using Python package `ascii-magic` 2.3.0 using both ANSI colors and full RGB colors. For the scale, a 100-column wide ASCII transformation was used.

In the Google Colab environment, the chosen classifier models VGG19, ResNet50, InceptionV3, MobileNet, and EfficientNetB0 are initialized with the readily provided ImageNet weights.

Each image in the reference dataset and the experimental obfuscated datasets are then fed to each classifier. Correct classifications are counted. In addition, incorrect classifications are recorded and the most common incorrect classifications are examined.

III. RESULTS

First, I will present the classification results for the reference dataset containing the original photos. Next, I will provide the results for the experimental obfuscated dataset. The results for the obfuscated data will be organized by object type (cats and dogs), by type of ASCII transformation (ANSI or RGB color), and by the CNN models used.

A. Reference Dataset

The reference dataset was fed to all chosen classifiers to check that the classifiers are capable of classifying the required images. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I
CLASSIFICATION ACCURACIES FOR THE REFERENCE DATASET

Model	Cats	Dogs
VGG19	9 / 10	10 / 10
ResNet50	9 / 10	10 / 10
InceptionV3	10 / 10	10 / 10
MobileNet	9 / 10	10 / 10
EfficientNetB0	10 / 10	10 / 10

As expected, the classification accuracy is excellent. Totally 97 classifications out of one hundred were correct. InceptionV3 and EfficientNetB0 made no misclassifications. The three incorrect classes were *toilet_seat*, *bath_towel*, and *sleeping_bag*.

Fig. 7. The most common classifications for the experimental obfuscated dataset by model

B. Experiment Obfuscated Datasets

All images in the experimental obfuscated datasets were recognizable to humans with low effort. However, none of the models with ImageNet weights was able to recognize any of the images.

The five most common incorrect classifications are provided for both ANSI and full RGB images in Table 2.

TABLE II
THE MOST COMMON INCORRECT CLASSIFICATIONS FOR THE EXPERIMENTAL OBFUSCATED DATASET

Class	ANSI	RGB
Cats	window_screen (25 times) prayer_rug (4 times) jean (4 times) radiator (4 times) brass (3 times)	window_screen: 46 times chain_mail: 1 times loudspeaker: 1 times radiator: 1 times brass: 1 times
Dogs	window_screen (17) prayer_rug (14 times) website (4 times) book_jacket (4 times) brass (2 times)	window_screen: 47 times brass (2 times) menu (1 times) - -

Misclassifications by model are presented in Fig. 7. Using full RGB colors makes most models more likely to misidentify ASCII images as window screens.

IV. DISCUSSION

First, I will discuss the findings of this study, followed by some potential directions for future research.

A. Results of this Study

This study demonstrates that converting images into ASCII representations using widely available tools effectively serves as a successful obfuscation technique. The commonly employed convolutional neural network classifiers failed to classify any of the cat and dog images in the obfuscated experimental datasets.

Fig. 8. Example images of a window screen (left) and prayer rug (right) from the ImageNet dataset.

Furthermore, the failed classifications indicate that the models are not merely misidentifying the targets but are instead deceived by the grid structure created by the ASCII characters. Typical images from the ImageNet dataset representing window screen and prayer rug are presented in the Fig. 8. These two most common incorrect categories have grid-like patterns that are the probable causes of misidentification.

Generally, such "tricks" as a single method of obfuscation hold limited significance. However, given that ASCII coding is a widely used, easily available, and well-known technique, it retains importance. There is a substantial imbalance in the effort required: while image-to-ASCII transformation is commonly available on Linux operating systems and in Python programming language, the reverse process is not as straightforward.

It is important to note that this method of obfuscation is not a permanent solution. Reversing the process and bypassing the obfuscation is likely not difficult. But, as shown in this paper, it can be successfully used with current out-of-the-box technologies.

This study focused on a single obfuscation technique which has quite a special role in computing; ASCII characters are the basic alphabet of human-computer communication. The study taps into the deep-rooted and symbolic role that ASCII plays in computing. The technique leverages ASCII's dual nature as both a fundamental tool for communication and a means of abstracting visual data into a simplified, text-based format. This approach not only reflects the historical and functional importance of ASCII in the evolution of computing but also opens up new avenues for exploring how such foundational elements can be repurposed in innovative ways.

B. Future Research

While CNNs and large language models frequently produce results that amaze both laymen and experts alike, it is instructive to identify tasks that remain easy for humans but challenging for these models. The results of this study are clear: none of the models pre-trained with ImageNet weights were able to recognize any of the ASCII-transformed images. This highlights a key area for future work: tracking the progress of neural models in learning to generalize effectively.

In this study, it was found that the most common CNNs did not recognize any ASCII-obfuscated images. This raises the question of whether we can find the limit of what is still recognizable and track how this limit evolves over time. This would involve varying fonts, typographical settings, and image types to create a comprehensive database of ASCII images.

Secondly, creating images using text has long been applied in art, decorations, advertisements, and for recreational purposes, such as hiding messages or creating puzzles. Often, these applications involve visual insight, aesthetic considerations, and other forms of creativity. These kinds of ideas are closely related to general intelligence and represent interesting long-term benchmarks for developing human-level artificial intelligence.

In addition, a specific area for future research is addressing the challenges posed by masks and textures that impede accurate image recognition and classification. A window screen was the most frequently misclassified class in this study. Similarly, fog or smoke, semitransparent screens, fences, and vegetation create blocking or closing effects. Robustness against these is generally desirable and this area is a hot topic of research. ASCII character images and text art, along with the blending of symbolic and natural image recognition, create a new dimension in these endeavours.

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